

Synthetic Studies of some Polymaleimides and Copolymaleimides

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Poly(*N*-arylmaleimides) and copolymaleimides have been prepared. The monomers (i) *N*-(4-*p*-toluidinylphenyl)maleimide, (ii) *N*-(4-methylphenyl)maleimide and (iii) *N*-(2-naphthyl)maleimide are prepared from the corresponding amines via maleamic acids and cyclodehydration. The homopolymerization of the monomers is initiated free-radically using azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) initiated in dimethylformamide (DMF). The monomers are also copolymerized with 4-vinylpyridine (4-VP) free-radically in DMF using equimolar amounts of the comonomers. Both the homo- and co-polymaleimides have been characterised by ir and ¹H nmr spectra. The solubility, thermal and some other properties of the monomers and polymers have been studied.

Free radical polymerization of *N*-substituted-maleimides using azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) or benzoyl peroxide (Bz₂O₂) as initiator has been reported by several workers¹. It has been observed that poly(*N*-arylmaleimides) show superior thermal properties compared to *N*-alkylmaleimides.

The rigidity of polymaleimides due to chain symmetry tends to make them intractable. The principle of copolymerization has been tried to reduce the chain symmetry and consequently increase the flexibility². Maleimides and related compounds have been copolymerized with compounds like ethylene, styrene, butadiene, α -methylstyrene, vinyl ether, acrylonitrile, methyl acrylate, methacrylic acid and vinyl chloride³. But very little work has been reported on the copolymerization of maleimides with vinyl comonomers containing heteroaromatic nucleus.

The present work reports the synthesis and characterisation of *N*-(4-*p*-toluidinylphenyl)maleimide (M₁), *N*-(4-methylphenyl)maleimide (M₂), *N*-(2-naphthyl)maleimide (M₃), their homopolymers as well as their copolymers with 4-vinylpyridine (4-VP).

Results and Discussion

The three maleimides were prepared from the corresponding amines via the amic acids and cyclodehydration. A summary of the polymerization conditions and physical characteristics of the homo- and copolymers are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Solubilities of the polymers are listed in Table 3. The polymaleimides and copolymaleimides are characterised by ir and ¹H nmr spectra.

The ir spectra exhibited peaks at 1 780 and 1 710–1 720 cm⁻¹ which are characteristics of five-membered cyclic imides. A comparative study of the monomers and their homopolymers reveals that the monomer bands at 3 100 (olefinicCH) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=C) are absent in the spectra of the polymers. On the other hand, a band at 2 960 cm⁻¹ (C–H of tertiary C–H) appears in the spectrum of the polymers P₂ and P₃. In the spectrum of P₁ this band is obscured due to the presence of bands at 2 940 cm⁻¹ (C–H of –CH₂–).

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF POLYMERIZATION OF SUBSTITUTED MALEIMIDES*

Polymer	Reaction condition		Colour	Yield %	[η] dl g ⁻¹
	<i>t</i> h	Precipitation medium			
P ₁	4.5	Water	Brown	60.0	0.080
P ₂	4.5	Water	Light brown	53.3	0.052
P ₃	4.5	Methanol	Purple	48.7	0.125

*P₁ = Poly-*N*-(4-*p*-toluidinylphenyl)maleimide; P₂ = poly-*N*-(4-methylphenyl)maleimide; P₃ = poly-*N*-(2-naphthyl)maleimide, *t* = time; [η] = intrinsic viscosity; AIBN concn. = 0.03 mol dm⁻³.

TABLE 2—REACTION CONDITIONS AND PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COPOLYMERS*

Polymer	Amount of comonomers feed (mmol)		Colour	Yield %	[η] dl g ⁻¹
	Maleimide	4-VP			
	P ₄	3.95			
P ₅	7.20	7.20	Purple	42.65	0.164
P ₆	10.40	10.40	Brown	65.67	0.185

*P₄ = Copolymer of *N*-(4-*p*-toluidinylphenyl)maleimide and 4-VP; P₅ = copolymer of *N*-(4-methylphenyl)maleimide and 4-VP; P₆ = copolymer of *N*-(2-naphthyl)maleimide and 4-VP; reaction condition : *t* = 3 h, AIBN concn. = 0.03 mol dm⁻³, precipitation medium = methanol.

TABLE 3—SOLUBILITY CHARACTERISTICS OF POLYMERS*

Solvent	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₄	P ₅	P ₆
Water	-	-	-	-	-	-
Absolute EtOH	-	-	-	-	-	-
MeOH	-	-	-	-	-	-
Acetone	+	++	+	-	+	+
DMF	++	++	++	++	++	++
Diethyl ether	+	+	-	-	-	+
Benzene	+	++	-	+	-	-
DMSO	++	++	++	++	++	++
Dichloromethane	-	++	+	-	-	++
Chloroform	+	++	+	++	+	++
THF	++	++	++	+	+	++

*(-) = Insoluble, (+) = Soluble, (++) = highly soluble.

From this it may be concluded that π -bond in C=C of a maleimide monomer undergoes homolytic cleavage facilitating the formation of a polymer.

The ir spectra of the copolymers P₄, P₅ and P₆ also reveal the absence of bands due to $\nu_{C=C}$ in the inside monomers. In P₄ and P₅ the band at 1 320 cm⁻¹ appears to be a doublet. This may be due to slight difference between C-N stretching frequency of Ar-N and C \equiv N stretching frequency of the pyridine ring. In case of P₆, however, the Ar-N stretching frequency (1 470 cm⁻¹) and C \equiv N stretching frequency of pyridine (1 350 cm⁻¹) are widely separated.

¹H nmr spectra of the maleimides and the polymers showed the following chemical shifts. *Monomers*: M₁, δ 6.1 (2H,olefinic), 6.8 (2H, NH₂), 2.5 (2H,CH₂), 7.1-7.6 (8H, ArH); M₂, δ 6.0 (2H, olefinic), 2.3 (3H, ϕ -CH₃), 7.2-7.5 (4H, ArH); M₃ δ 6.1 (2H, olefinic), 7-7.8 (7H, ArH). *Polymers*: P₁ δ 2.05-2.1 (2H, CH), 2.5 (CH₂, 2H), 6.8 (2H, NH₂), 7.1-7.4 (8H, ArH); P₂ δ 2.1 (2H, CH), 2.3 (3H, ϕ -CH₃), 7.1-7.4 (4H, ArH); P₃ δ 2.1 (2H, CH), 7-7.78 (7H, ArH); P₄ δ 2.0(3H,CH), 2.4-2.6 (4H, CH₂), 6.8 (2H, NH₂), 7.1-8.5 (13H, ArH); P₅ δ 2-2.2 (3H, CH), 7-7.8 (13H, ArH); P₆ δ 2.1 (3H, CH), 7-8.5 (13H, ArH).

From the ¹H nmr spectra it was observed that the chemical shift at δ 6.0 (due to olefinic proton) in maleimide disappeared in the spectra of the polymers. On the other hand, appearance of peak at δ 2.1-2.2 in the polymers due to saturated CH confirms that polymerization has taken place through the olefinic double bond of the imide ring. In the copolymers, the peaks at δ 8-8.4 (protons of pyridine ring) confirm the incorporation of 4-vinylpyridine into the polymers. Hence the polyaddition reactions can be represented as shown in Scheme 1.

Ar = Aromatic moiety of the maleimide

Scheme 1

Thermal study: The TGA and DTG curves of each of the polymers show an slight initial weight-loss upto nearly 100°, which may be attributed to the removal of absorbed moisture or entrapped solvent. From the TGA and DTG curves, the initial decomposition temperature (IDT) and maximum decomposition temperature (DT_{max}) have been

calculated (Table 4). The results reveal that the homopoly-maleimides are more thermostable than the corresponding copolymaleimides. This is attributable to the incorporation of the flexible -CH₂-CH- links into the chain backbone of the copolymers in contrast to the homopolymers which bear cyclic five- membered ring in the polymer chain.

TABLE 4-IDT AND DT_{max} FOR POLYMERS

Polymer	IDT (°C)	DT _{max} (°C)
P ₁	340	450
P ₂	330	410
P ₃	365	470
P ₄	290	350
P ₅	300	350
P ₆	290	360

Experimental

Maleic anhydride, 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane, *p*-toluidine, β -naphthylamine, DMF, AIBN and methanol were purified by the usual procedure.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in DMSO-d₆. TGA and DTG studies were done in a Shimadzu DT 30B instrument in air at a heating rate of 10°/min. Viscosity was measured in DMSO at 30° using an a Ubbelohde viscometer.

To determine the solubility behaviour of the polymers, each of the polymer sample (0.002 g) was placed in different solvents (2 ml), shaken well and allowed to stand overnight and then checked whether dissolution took place or not.

The monomers and maleimides were prepared from the corresponding amines via the maleamic acids. A typical run is as follows. A mixture of maleic anhydride (2.45 g, 25 mmol) and 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (4.95 g, 25 mmol) separately dissolved in acetone (50 ml), was stirred for 1 h. The mixture was then poured into distilled water (250 ml) and stirred. The resulting light brown precipitate of maleamic acid was washed with distilled water and dried. To the maleamic acid (4 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) were added freshly distilled acetic anhydride (10 ml) and fused sodium acetate (1 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h in a water-bath at 100°. It was then cooled and poured into a large volume of cold distilled water. The resulting precipitate of maleimide was washed with distilled water and dried: *N*-(4-*p*-toluidinylphenyl)maleimic acid, m.p. 322°, acid value 185.96 mg KOH/g (calcd 189.19); *N*-(4-methylphenyl)maleamic acid, 190°, 272.31 (273.17); *N*-(2-naphthyl)maleamic acid, 182°, 232.46 (232.37); M₁, 226°; M₂ 130°; M₃ 130°.

Polymerization reactions were performed in a one-limbed tube of corning glass. The tube containing the monomer and AIBN in DMF was completely degassed, sealed, immersed in a thermostat at $60 \pm 0.01^\circ$ and after a few hours the polymer was precipitated into methanol.

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